

SEARCH FOR NEW INSECTICIDES. PART II

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o-Hydroxyketones of five esters of 4-chloro-3:5-dimethylphenol have been prepared by the Fries migration and have been converted into their allyl ethers with a view to studying their insecticidal activity.

In continuation of our previous work (Tiwari *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 766; 1957, 34, 830), we have now prepared allyl derivatives of hydroxyketones obtained by the rearrangement of esters of 4-chloro-3:5-dimethylphenol.

In keeping with the observation of Lauger *et al.* (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1944, 27, 918) that allyloxy or aryl ethers are good contact insecticides because of their having a combination of toxic and lipid-soluble grouping in their molecule, we have prepared five compounds containing allyl groups as toxophores and the ether linkage having lipophilic properties (cf. Chen and Sumerford, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 4694). These compounds also contain chlorine atom in the nucleus which might increase the toxicity, and ketonic group which might increase the lipid solubility.

Five esters of *p*-chloro-*m*-xylenol, viz., propionate, butyrate, valerate, caproate and heptylate, were obtained either by Chattaway's method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 2495) or by Spasov's method (*Chem. Abst.*, 1940, 2343).

The Fries rearrangement in the present investigation was studied at 110° with or without solvent. In all these cases studied, *o*-hydroxyketones were obtained, as confirmed by Pyman's test (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 280).

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The five esters of *p*-chloro-*m*-xylenol, prepared according to methods described previously (cf. Sen and Tiwari, this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 358), are described in Table I.

TABLE I

<i>p</i> -Chloro- <i>m</i> -xylenol esters.	%Yield.	B.P.	Formula.	%Carbon.		%Hydrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1. Propionate	78.0	123°/3 mm	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₂ Cl	62.07	62.13	6.11	6.12
2. Butyrate	62.0	135°/3	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ O ₂ Cl	63.41	63.57	6.61	6.62
3. Valerate	85.0	269°/7	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ O ₂ Cl	64.80	64.86	7.06	7.07
4. Caproate	89.0	145°/1	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ O ₂ Cl	65.70	66.10	7.44	7.47
5. Heptylate	79.0	174°/3	C ₁₅ H ₂₁ O ₂ Cl	67.00	67.04	7.67	7.82

* Prepared by Chattaway's method.

Fries Rearrangement of the Esters.—The ester (1.0 M) was rearranged by keeping it with anhydrous aluminium chloride (1.5 M) in anhydrous CS₂ (6.0 M), for 2 hours at 80°. After distilling off the solvent the temperature of the mixture was raised to 110° and maintained at 110° for 2 hours. The hydroxyketones were isolated, purified and characterised in the usual way (Table II).

TABLE II

<i>p</i> -Chloro- <i>m</i> -xyleneol esters.	Ketone formed.	Cryst. from.	Cryst. shape.	Yield	M.P.	%Carbon. Found. Calc.		%Hydrogen. Found. Calc.	
1. Propionate	R-ethyl-K	EtOH	Yellowish white	76%	106°	62.04	62.13	6.11	6.12
2. Butyrate	R- <i>n</i> -propyl*-K	Do	Do	96	76°	63.31	63.7	6.61	6.62
3. Valerate	R- <i>n</i> -butyl-K	Do	White	73	63°	64.76	64.86	7.03	7.07
4. Caproate	R- <i>n</i> -amyl-K**	EtOH or AcOH	Do	86	80°	65.87	65.10	7.40	7.47
5. Heptylate	R- <i>n</i> -hexyl-K	Do	Do	69	79°	66.59	67.04	7.81	7.82

Semicarbazone.

Mol. formula	M.P.	%Nitrogen.	
		Found.	Calc.
1. C ₁₂ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	212°	15.95	15.95
C ₁₇ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	225°	15.71	15.81
3. C ₁₂ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	200°	13.92	14.12
4. C ₁₅ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	152°	13.47	13.49
5. C ₁₈ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	154°	12.55	12.90

* Using CS₂ as solvent.

** Without solvent yield is very poor.

N.B. Molecular formula of the ketone is the same as that of the ester.

-K denotes ketone; R- denotes 2-hydroxy-5-chloro-4:6-dimethylphenyl-.

The *o*-hydroxyketones, obtained by the Fries rearrangement of these esters, were characterised through their semicarbazones (Table II), as 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones could not be isolated.

These *o*-hydroxyketones were further converted into allyl ethers (Table III), but these ethers could not be converted into their 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones or semicarbazones.

TABLE III

Hydroxyketones.	Ether formed.	Yield.	B.P.	Formula.	%Carbon. Found. Calc.		%Hydrogen. Found. Calc.	
					Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1. R-ethyl-K	R'-ethyl-K	81%	54° (un p.)	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ O ₂ Cl	66.44	66.53	6.72	6.73
2. R- <i>n</i> -propyl-K	R'- <i>n</i> -propyl-K	95	158°/1 mm	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ O ₂ Cl	67.50	67.54	7.08	7.13
3. R- <i>n</i> -butyl-K	R'- <i>n</i> -butyl-K	98	160°/3	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ O ₂ Cl	68.36	68.43	7.45	7.49
4. R- <i>n</i> -amyl-K	R'- <i>n</i> -amyl-K	69	190°/2	C ₁₇ H ₂₃ O ₂ Cl	69.20	69.28	7.71	7.81
5. R- <i>n</i> -hexyl-K	R'- <i>n</i> -hexyl-K	87	187°/2	C ₁₈ H ₂₅ O ₂ Cl	69.88	70.01	7.90	8.10

N.B. Semicarbazone and 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone not separated.

K-denotes ketone; R' denotes 2-allyloxy-5-chloro-4:6-dimethylphenyl-.

R-denotes 2-hydroxy-5-chloro-4:6-dimethylphenyl-.

Allyl-aryl Ethers.—A mixture of allyl bromide (0.11 M), freshly fused potassium carbonate (0.11 M) and anhydrous acetone (40 c.c.) was refluxed on a water-bath for 6 hours. After cooling, ice was added and acetone was distilled off. The oily layer was taken in ether. The ethereal layer was washed with 5% NaOH solution several times, then with the distilled water and dried over freshly fused potassium carbonate. The ether was then removed by distillation and the residual oil was distilled under reduced pressure (Table III).

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